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Summary

Agriculture is one of the main causes of biodiversity decline worldwide. Several scenarios for biodiversity-friendly agriculture have already been modelled at European level, demonstrating their biophysical feasibility. However, their socio-economic implications still need to be explored, as well as the policies that would enable to address these. This is the purpose of this study, which is Deliverable 1.2 of the Transformative Change for Biodiversity & Equity project (TC4BE). To this end, we (i) conducted interviews with public policy actors to better understand what new research and evidence they need to design better policies in support of the transition, (ii) conducted a bibliographic analysis of the literature on the costs and the mechanisms of the transition, (iii) carried out a case study examining the socio-economic implications of a biodiversity-friendly agricultural scenario on the food processing industry in the Champagne-Ardenne region.

Our interviews with experts show that policy makers want to understand the changes involved in the transition and need to know its socio-economic consequences, going beyond a “simple” (yet already complicated) costing. Secondly, our literature review highlights three main gaps: a lack of analysis of biodiversity and of the consequences of the transition on the agri-food industry, as well as the need to better characterize the structural changes in production tools linked to the transition. Finally, modelling a biodiversity-friendly scenario and crop rotation with a view to diversity and circularity, allows us to analyse how a biodiversity-friendly scenario impacts the volumes allocated to industries in our study region. This case study identified three types of industries that are impacted differently by the biodiversity-friendly scenario: (i) industries that are maintaining their position (processing primary cereals and potatoes), whose supply is maintained but whose production costs are likely to increase; (ii) declining industries (processing sugar beet and rapeseed), which suffer from supply disruptions. Some of them will have to close, resulting in stranded assets of around €1,518 million and the loss of 930 jobs. (iii) Industries to be developed and created (processing hemp, dehydrated alfalfa, protein crops and secondary cereals), for which processing volumes are increasing. The need to create new factories will require an investment of €920 million and the creation of 1,060 jobs. This analysis highlights the need for different public policies for each type of industry, resulting in significant and varied requirements. The main needs identified are: (i) support for competitiveness for industries that are maintaining their position; (ii) social support for industries in decline; (iii) support for demand, the creation of industrial tools, production and the organisation of sectors for industries to be developed and created.

1. Introduction

The purpose of this report as deliverable 3.1 of the TC4BE project is to propose public policy recommendations that support agriculture compatible with a high level of biodiversity.

Agriculture accounts for more than a third of the Earth's land surface and is one of the main causes of biodiversity decline (IPBES, 2019). Biodiversity plays a vital role in the existence and well-being of the human population (Ibid.). There is therefore an urgent need to develop public policies that promote the transition to agriculture that is compatible with a high level of biodiversity.

García-(2024) propose 11 limits that must not be exceeded in order for agriculture to be compatible with biodiversity conservation. These limits imply significant changes to current European agricultural systems, particularly in terms of diversity and circularity which would have significant impacts on the product mix, i.e. the quantity and nature of agricultural production, and therefore on the entire European agri-food chain. The biophysical feasibility of such scenarios has already been studied by (Poux & Aubert, 2018) at European level and in D1.1 by BIODIVA at global level, but their social and economic implications have not been studied in depth. Yet, policy makers are directly interested by these socio-economic issues: they can indeed influence the socio-economic conditions conducive to the transition through public policy, and they must ensure the social and economic feasibility of the desired change to guarantee the well-being of the population. In order to make the best policy decisions, they need access to knowledge about the environmental, social and economic consequences of a biodiversity-friendly transition.

The significant change in the product mix envisaged in this scenario would have consequences throughout the value chain, from farm to fork. The consequences of sustainable agri-food transitions have already been studied at both ends of the chain, on the farm side (Aubert, Gardin, Alliot, et al., 2021; Guyomard et al., 2023; Pellerin et al., 2013, 2020; Van Der Ploeg et al., 2019) and consumers (Guyomard et al., 2023; IDDRI & I4CE, 2025; Rockström et al., 2025). However, the intermediate link in the agri-food industry has been little studied. Yet this link is at the heart of agri-food systems. Industries can both impact agricultural practices through their sourcing strategies and influence consumption practices through the products they offer. Given that the agri-food industries represent an important economic sector and a major source of employment in France and Europe (FoodDrinkEurope, 2023; Ministry of Agriculture and Food Sovereignty, 2024), it is crucial to assess the challenges of the transition for this link.

That is why we have chosen to make policy recommendations on how to address **the socio-economic impact of an agricultural-biodiversity-friendly transition on the agri-food industries.**

To answer this question, this study consists of three chapters. A first chapter is based on interviews with experts and public policy actors and aims to define as accurately as possible the need of policy makers regarding new evidence / knowledge regarding the socio-economic challenges of the transition. A second chapter reviews the literature on the costs of the transition to explore whether existing research actually meets policy makers' needs. A third chapter focuses on a case study conducted in a French region. The consequences of a biodiversity-friendly agricultural scenario on the agri-food industry is analysed in a three steps approach: we modelled an agricultural scenario with a high level of diversification in the region; we then looked at how agricultural raw material flows were redistributed amongst the different industries; we examined the implications for the industry in terms of stranded assets, investment needs and the associated job losses and creation.

The results are as follows. First, our interviews with experts and public policy actors showed that policy makers want to be more informed about the technical and socio-economic transformations involved by the transition. Furthermore, describing the concrete changes was more relevant than calculating an overall cost.

Secondly, the literature review reveals three characteristics of the existing literature on the cost of the transition: (i) the literature mainly addresses the issue of the cost of the transition from a climate perspective, and tend to overlook biodiversity questions, (ii) the literature mostly assesses the economic implications of the transition without considering structural changes – e.g. mostly quantifying the costs of technical / technological changes, but with limited to no attention paid to the fact that future farms and future industries will be structurally different than today; (iii) the literature does not study the consequences of the transition on the agri-food industry.

Thirdly, we show that the economic impacts of the transition are heterogeneous. On the one hand, stranded assets are significant: they represent €1,518 million at current costs, while investment needs would amount to €990 million. However, the total number of jobs created (1,060) would exceed the number of jobs lost (932). While the impact is therefore potentially positive, it also raises questions in terms of training, transfers between sectors, etc. To arrive at these results, the study is based on a typology of industries according to the changes envisaged and the associated public policy needs.

- A first type of industry concerns sectors whose production volumes are declining due to diversification, but where a significant proportion of volumes are currently not used for non-industrial uses (mainly exports: primary cereals and potatoes). The remaining volumes are thus theoretically sufficient to run existing facilities at near to full capacity. Two supporting challenges are emerging for public policy: (1) maintaining the competitiveness of the processing units that remain; (2) managing trading partners affected by the decline in exports.
- The second category concerns sectors whose production volumes would decline to such an extent that facilities currently present on the territory could not be any more supplied with enough volume. Some plants will thus have to wind down their activities (sugar beet and rapeseed). Specific measures are therefore needed to manage these stranded assets and the associated job losses (replacement of employees, training, etc.).
- The third category concerns sectors whose production volumes are increasing and for which industrial tools either need to be developed on an already existing solid basis (hemp, dehydrated alfalfa), or require to be created nearly from scratch (protein crops such as peas, soya, lentils and field beans, as well as minor cereals such as triticale, oats, rye and durum wheat). Support policies are needed at four levels: to support agricultural production, the creation of new industrial tools, demand, and to assist with the organisation of the sectors.

2. Materials and methods

We used three approaches to address the public policy challenges of a biodiversity-friendly scenario. First, a series of interviews with experts and policy makers aimed to define the need for new knowledge regarding (1) the costs and transformations incurred by the transition and (2) the policy measures to be deployed in each sector. These needs were then compared with the literature characterizing the costs and mechanisms of the transition. Finally, we conducted a case study combining quantitative industry analyses, agronomic modelling and interviews with stakeholders in the sectors to address our research question.

Expert interviews

We conducted two phases of interviews with experts. The first phase aimed to define the needs of policy makers. The second phase aimed to improve our understanding of the agri-food sectors we studied in our case study.

For the first phase, two types of stakeholders were interviewed: (i) public administration officials working directly for or with policy makers (4 interviews) and (ii) scientific experts who had participated in research aimed at informing policy decisions (3 interviews). For public administration staff, the aim of the interviews was to understand what new knowledge / evidence do they need the most to support the design / acceptability of accompanying policies. For scientific experts, the aim of the interviews was to analyse how their various works on the cost of the transition had been used by different stakeholders to inform and influence public policy.

In a second phase, various experts were consulted in order to deepen our knowledge of the different agri-food sectors analysed in this study. The types of experts/institutions consulted are listed in Table 1

1 Table: List of experts/institutions consulted to deepen our knowledge

Type of expert/institution	Sector	Number of interviews
Cooperative	Hemp	1
Agricultural advisor	Field crops	1
Members of the European Commission's Directorate-General for Agriculture, Economic Sustainability Unit	Agri-food industries	1
Technical Institute	Oilseeds and protein crops	1
Industrial technical centre	Plant protein and cereals	1
Professional representative	Food processing industries Mill Alfalfa	3
Researchers		2
National Institute for Agricultural and Marine Products	Field crops	1
Innovation hub	Field crops	1

Literature review on the cost of transition

Once the expectations of policy makers had been defined, we conducted a bibliographic analysis to assess how the literature responds to the needs of policy makers. One of the main needs that emerged was to know the cost of the transition, which is what we focused our research on.

The aim of this bibliographic analysis was not to provide an exhaustive list of existing work, but rather to analyse the work that is used to inform public policy. This is why we relied in particular on our interviews to select the work that is currently considered authoritative. To fully understand how the issue of transition costs is addressed, we first looked at the literature dealing with the cost of

low-carbon transition across all sectors, as many studies have been carried out on this subject and are used by public authorities. We then focused on studies analysing transitions in the agricultural sector. Finally, we studied existing work on biodiversity-related costs.

The literature was analysed using the following set of questions:

- What scale is being studied (geographical, sector, link in the agri-food system)?
- What kind of changes are being considered (technological change, structural change, change in production volumes)?
- What are the considerations regarding capital intensity and labour intensity?
- What economic impact is being assessed (investment needs, changes in production costs, impact on whom)?
- How are social issues taken into account?
- Are stranded assets taken into account?
- Is the strategy of economic actors being studied?
- How is the transition envisaged being handled by public policy?

Case study

The two previous steps highlighted the relevance of studying a specific case study. The objective of this case study is to analyse the challenges that a biodiversity-friendly transition raises for public policy in a particular region and sector, given its socio-economic implications. We focused on the consequences of this transition for the agri-food industries (AFI) that process arable crops in Champagne-Ardenne. Below, we present (i) the type of biodiversity-friendly transition we modelled, (ii) the choice of the study region, (iii) the method used to model the biodiversity-friendly biophysical scenario, and (iv) the method used to assess the scenario's impacts on the region's industries.

The type of biodiversity-friendly transition envisaged

For our case study, we modelled the same type of agricultural transition as that modelled in D1.1. We take into account the limits that must not be exceeded in agriculture in order to maintain a high level of biodiversity, as defined by García-Vega et al.(2024). Such a scenario has already been modelled at the European level in the TYFA scenario (Poux & Aubert, 2018) . It has also been modelled by the BIODIVA model at the global level in D1.1.

The 11 limits defined by García-Vega et al.(2024) , imply profound changes in agricultural systems:

- Limiting agricultural land.
- Reducing greenhouse gas emissions from agriculture
- Restrict the use of water available for agriculture.
- Reducing pesticide use to less than 50% of current average use in Europe.
- Reducing the use of nitrogen and phosphorus
- Have a minimum of 20% semi-natural elements per km² of cultivated land
- Increase crop diversity (mixed cropping, agroforestry systems)
- Increase the complexity and length of crop rotations.
- Manage grasslands extensively (no fertilisation, limited stocking rates)

Various studies on Europe (Poux & Aubert, 2018; Röös et al., 2017; Van Selm et al., 2022; Van Zanten et al., 2018) clearly show that such changes have a significant impact on the *product mix*, i.e. the quantity and nature of agricultural production. In most of the scenarios discussed, these changes imply a shift in dietary patterns, which will not be addressed in this study. On this point, reference can be made to recent work by IDDRI & I4CE(2025) .

The choice of case study

We have chosen to study the socio-economic challenges of a biodiversity-friendly transition for the agri-food industries that process arable crops in Champagne-Ardenne. Such a transition in the arable crop sector raises issues of diversification and circularity that are considered important by policy makers. In addition, work has already been done on the impact of such a scenario for the dairy sector (Aubert, Gardin, Huber, et al., 2021) and meat (Schiavo et al., 2025) . It was therefore decided to focus on crop production. Field crops represent the largest areas of plant production, accounting for 44% of utilised agricultural area (UAA) and 66% of UAA excluding permanent grassland in France(calculations based on Agreste, 2021) .

Champagne-Ardenne is a former agricultural region located in eastern France. It is located in the new Grand-Est region and comprises four departments: Ardennes (08), Aube (10), Marne (51) and Haute-Marne (52) (see Figure 1).

Figure 1 : Map of Champagne-Ardenne in France

The region specialises in arable farming, which accounts for more than 40% of crop rotation in the Ardennes and Haute-Marne, and more than 60% of crop rotation in the Marne and Aube (Agreste, 2024). Champagne-Ardenne also accounts for 13% of French arable crop production (calculations based on Agreste, 2020). In addition, the region's arable crops are quite diverse. This region has both large areas of cereal and oilseed crops, which account for 63% of its crop rotation and 10% of national production, as well as industrial crops, with 101,000 ha of sugar beet (22% of national production) and 20,300 ha of potatoes (11% of national production) (calculations based on Agreste 2020). Sectors that are beneficial to biodiversity and crop rotation diversification already exist, such as dehydrated alfalfa and industrial hemp. Finally, the European Bioeconomy Centre, which promotes large volumes of field crops, has been developed in Bazancourt.

Modelling the biophysical scenario

In order to assess the impact of a biodiversity-friendly scenario, we first modelled a biophysical scenario. This scenario projects a crop rotation compatible with a high level of biodiversity in terms of crop diversity. We used the crop rotation adopted in BIODIVA, taken from Barbieri et al., (2019), , adapting it to the Champagne-Ardenne region. We used the 2020 crop rotation as a reference point for the current situation, based on data from the annual agricultural statistics and the 2020 agricultural census. Both are produced by the national agricultural statistics agency Agreste.

Assessment of the impact on the agri-food industries

Once the biophysical scenario had been developed, the objective was to assess the impact of the change in crop rotation on the region's agri-food industries (AFI). We limited the study to primary processing industries that process field crops. In addition to field crops, dehydrated alfalfa is also included in the study. This crop is an integral part of the region's specialised field crop production systems.

To carry out this assessment, we used various data sources, as well as expert opinions and participatory workshops with local stakeholders.

The Table 1 below describes the various steps involved in the assessment and the data sources used.

Table 1 : Steps and data sources for assessing the impact on the agri-food industries

Steps	Data sources
Mapping of agri-food industries present in Champagne-Ardenne	FLORES establishment (INSEE), company websites, DRAAF Grand Est
Mapping of agricultural flows processed by different agri-food industries	PRODCOM Commercialised production of agri-food industries (Ministry of Agriculture), company websites, newspaper articles, expert interviews
Socio-economic characterisation of agri-food industries	FARE Annual structural business statistics from the ESAN system (INSEE and Ministry of Finance), company websites, newspaper articles, expert opinions
Mapping of new agricultural flows processed by different agri-food industries in the biodiversity-friendly scenario	Own modelling
Assessment of the impact of the change in flows to agri-food industries on investment needs, stranded assets, job creation and job losses	Own calculation
Analysis of public policy needs to support the anticipated impacts	Own analysis

The socio-economic characterisation of the IAA was carried out using two indicators. Firstly, capital intensity in M€/kt, which corresponds to the investment required (or the tangible fixed assets of companies) to process 1,000 tonnes of raw materials. Secondly, employment intensity (FTE/kt), which corresponds to the number of full time equivalent required to process 1,000 tonnes of raw materials. These indices were calculated either at regional level, where the data were available and complied with statistical confidentiality, or at national level, where the data were only available at national level.

To model the raw material flows in the scenario, the volume of crops available was deducted from crop rotation at constant yield. This is a very strong assumption in the context of a biodiversity-friendly scenario, in which nitrogen constraints are significant (see D1.1). However, the effects at constant yields – i.e. solely linked to diversification – have already proved to be very significant. The volumes were allocated primarily to industrial use. Based on the new processed volumes and socio-economic indicators, we deduce the investment needs, stranded assets, job creation and job losses. We also analyse the industrial reconfigurations at stake in order to determine the support needs of the public authorities.

3. Result 1: interviews on the expectations of policy makers

Interviews with members of the French public administration revealed several things. First, and unsurprisingly, the public administration already uses scientific studies combining technical and economic elements to provide the best possible advice to policy makers. Access to technical and economic quantifications enables them to calibrate public policies as effectively as possible and choose the most appropriate measures. Previous studies from INRAE (2013, 2020), which compare different agricultural practices in terms of their cost-effectiveness to reduce emission of store carbon have been cited several times as references. These studies are also regularly updated by the technical services of the public administration.

Secondly, most of the actors we interviewed, who are most often personally convinced that a transition is needed, are looking for socio-economic evaluations that would demonstrate the economic viability of the transition. They see such results as essential elements to engage in a dialogue with economic stakeholders of the sectors, particularly those who are most sceptical about the transition. This requires knowledge of the impact of the transition on the various links in the value chain, as well as on macroeconomic factors such as competitiveness. More generally, these stakeholders want to be able to demonstrate the positive economic consequences of the transition – and tend not to be interested by results showing negative impacts.

Finally, the importance of having analyses that can be used "in real life" was emphasised. In particular, they felt it was necessary to have fairly detailed analyses by sector, enabling them to see what the transition would look like in concrete terms. In addition, they were looking for concrete public policy proposals.

As the stakeholders interviewed work at the national level, they were interested in analyses at the national level. They felt that comparisons with other European Union Member States would be relevant.

Our interviews with experts involved in policy making processes also enabled us to understand how their work had been used by policy-makers. It also gave us some insight into the expectations of policy-makers. First of all, studies with technical and economic elements have already been used to develop frameworks for public policy and private action. For example, the study of the marginal abatement cost for different agricultural decarbonisation practices was used to develop France's national low-carbon strategy (i.e. France's roadmap for combating climate change, developed by the Ministry for Ecological Transition). It also contributed to the creation of a low-carbon label in the agricultural sector, and some cooperatives have used it to encourage their members to adopt low-carbon practices.

It was also noted that economic and political actors were more sensitive to the description of the concrete changes brought about by the transition than to the overall cost of the transition. Indeed, an overall cost can be useful in comparison with the current funding allocated, in order to justify additional funding needs. On the other hand, describing the necessary changes makes it possible to appreciate the scale of the changes for production tools and the concrete consequences for the various players in the sectors.

Finally, the experts emphasised the importance of work combining technical and economic issues in order to structure the public debate on the transition.

Based on these interviews, two aspects seemed essential to us in order to best inform policy makers about the biodiversity-friendly transition through research work:

- Show what this transition would look like in concrete terms for stakeholders in the sectors and what changes would be involved for production tools.
- Incorporate assessments of technical, economic and social aspects.

4. Result 2: Bibliographic analysis

How scientific literature addresses the issue of transition costs

Firstly, the literature addresses the issue of financing the ecological transition mainly from the perspective of decarbonisation and energy challenges (McCOLLUM et al., 2013; OECD, 2017; Pisani-Ferry & Mahfouz, 2023; Rosslowe et al., 2022) . Agriculture is therefore a separate field, since the majority of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in agriculture are due to biophysical processes linked to agricultural practices rather than energy consumption (OECD, 2017; Pellerin et al., 2013) . Thus, the cost of the ecological transition in agriculture appears difficult to quantify and is rarely addressed in the mainstream literature costing emission reductions (Pisani-Ferry & Mahfouz, 2023) .

Nevertheless, there are several approaches to addressing this issue in agriculture, summarised in the 2 below.

Firstly, several studies address this issue from the perspective of abatement costs (Pellerin et al., 2013, 2020) . According to the commission (Criqui, 2021) , "The concept of the socio-economic abatement cost of a decarbonisation measure refers to the unit cost, from the community's point of view, of reducing GHG emissions. This involves comparing the cost of implementing the action with the total volume of GHG emissions avoided: this abatement cost is therefore expressed in €/tCO₂eq" (Criqui, 2021) . INRA has conducted two studies to calculate the abatement cost of agricultural practices, one on GHG reduction practices and the other on carbon storage practices (Pellerin et al., 2013, 2020). These studies provide a detailed analysis of the economic cost of each practice and compare them in terms of their cost and decarbonisation potential. However, the practices selected must not jeopardise the production system or lead to a drop of more than 10% in production levels (Pellerin et al., 2013). This type of analysis remains at the level of individual practices that are compared with each other.

Secondly, some studies view the transition as **an investment in green technologies** to replace brown technologies (Bueb et al., 2019; Pisani-Ferry & Mahfouz, 2023; Skidmore, 2023) . We can cite, for example, Bueb et al. (2019): "Investment is the key: it is what makes it possible to decouple greenhouse gas emissions from human activities." This substitution of technologies through investment is seen as an economic opportunity: "There is no future economy but green economy" (Skidmore, 2023). Among these exercises, Pisani-Ferry and Mahfouz (2023) attempted to calculate what these investments would represent for agriculture. However, they acknowledge the difficulty of the exercise for this sector and have only calculated the investments related to the decarbonisation of tractors, considering the reduction in livestock farming and fertiliser use as levers for sustainability that do not require additional investment. This "green investment" approach is therefore too partial to analyse the costs of the transition in the agricultural sector, whose transition relies also – and maybe foremost – on changes in practices and systems.

Many studies also use economic models (Ipcc, 2022) . Several types of models exist for the agricultural sector: microeconomic supply models, partial and general equilibrium models, and "engineering" models (Bamière et al., 2017) . We were particularly interested in partial equilibrium models. These models provide a detailed description of the agricultural sector and price formation following a change in supply and/or demand, which is itself linked to the implementation of policies (Ibid.). Potentially, a multitude of policies can be studied using these models. For example, (Guyomard et al., 2023) tested several Green Deal policies and their impacts on production prices, competitiveness, farmers' incomes, food expenditure and the environment. These models are very useful for seeing the impact of a change in supply/demand on prices and underlying economic mechanisms, but they reflect a constant system, which implies a transition without changes in the productive apparatus.

Finally, some studies are based on surveys trying to elucidate the willingness-to-adopt improved practices at the farm level (Wittow et al., 2023) . In this type of study, a questionnaire is sent to a sample of farmers proposing prices for adopting a practice or combination of practices (Conner et al., 2016) . This type of study makes it possible to obtain the perceived cost of adopting a new practice from farmers and compare it with existing subsidies for adopting the practice (Conner et al., 2016; Wittow et al., 2023). This provides an idea of the price required in addition to the technical cost,

reflecting the non-economic costs of adopting new practices. In addition, it is possible to test all types of practices. However, only a few individual practices are evaluated, and the systemic dimension is lacking.

2 below compares the different types of studies in the literature that have just been presented. It details their overall approach, the type of transformation evaluated, the type of economic evaluation, their advantages and their possible limitations for assessing the cost of transition.

What emerges from this table is also that studies looking at the cost of a biodiversity-friendly transition are relatively rare. One notable example is the Paulson Institute's Financing Nature study (Deutz et al., 2020) , which lists current funding and the funding needed for sustainable biodiversity management. Agriculture is one of the many sectors studied, for which they calculate the subsidies needed to support farmers' incomes during the transition of their systems to sustainable agriculture, which they define as soil conservation agriculture. The amount of aid required is calculated on the basis of the gross value of regional agricultural production. This approach considers that aid is only necessary during the 3- to 4-year transition phase. It is consistent with both the green investment approach, whereby systems are economically sustainable once the initial investment has been made, and the willingness to adopt approach, whereby income support is sufficient to bring about a transition by farmers.

It should be noted that in these studies, the analysis is either at the level of individual practice, at the level of the investments required to change technology, or at the level of the macroeconomic consequences of a change in production. In each case, the transition takes place within a constant system, i.e. the means of production (cropping systems and agri-food industries) remain structurally similar: only practices within these system are deemed to change. Furthermore, these different studies draw different conclusions about the transition, which may be economically positive or negative for producers and consumers (Deutz et al., 2020; Pellerin et al., 2013; Pisani-Ferry & Mahfouz, 2023) or negative (Guyomard et al., 2023) . We therefore felt it was necessary to better characterise the structural changes that the transition implies for these tools in order to shed more light on the positive or negative impact of the transition.

Furthermore, this research focuses mainly on the farm level and the consequences for consumers. However, the intermediate link of the agri-food industries is never studied. We therefore wanted to focus specifically on this link.

Rationale for a case study focused on the agrifood processing industry

Firstly, we have just seen that the agri-food industry link is never studied in studies dealing with the socio-economic consequences of the transition. However, the agri-food industry is a key player in the agri-food value chain. An agro-biodiversity-friendly transition involves developing crops that are currently underdeveloped and reducing certain crops that are currently dominant (Poux & Aubert, 2018) . However, agricultural production and industrial tools are closely linked (Gardin et al., 2024; Thomas et al., 2013) . On the one hand, minor crops can only develop if they are promoted in economically viable value chains (Meynard et al., 2018) , which implies the creation of outlets through agri-food industries. On the other hand, the decline in major crops could expose agri-food industries to economic risks. Furthermore, the agri-food industry is an important economic sector in France and Europe. It represents 4.6 million jobs and €1.1 billion in turnover in Europe (FoodDrinkEurope, 2023) , and 500,000 jobs and €212 million in turnover in France (Ministry of Agriculture and Food Sovereignty, 2024) . There is therefore a significant political challenge in supporting this sector and accompanying it through the transition, particularly in the face of a transition that would bring both opportunities and risks.

2 : Bibliographic analysis of the cost of the transition

Types of study	Abatement cost	Green investments	Partial equilibrium economic model	Willingness to adopt
Examples in the literature	(Pellerin et al., 2013, 2020)	(Pisani-Ferry & Mahfouz, 2023)	(Guyomard et al., 2023)	(Conner et al., 2016; Wittow et al., 2023)
Approach	Analysis of the technical cost of implementing different practices and comparison of their economic efficiency in relation to a defined objective	Technological substitution to switch to green energy through capital investment	Assessment of the impact of a public policy involving a change in supply and/or demand on the economic equilibrium of the market	Price at which a farmer is willing to change practices
Type of transformations envisaged	Adoption of practices	Change in technology Here: electrification of tractors	Variation in supply and/or demand Here: biophysical and dietary changes	Change in practice
Type of economic assessment	Cost of implementing practices	Investments required Macroeconomic impacts	Impact on land use, supply, producer prices and therefore on farmers' incomes, food expenditure and competitiveness	Price given to a change in practice
Interests	Detailed analysis of the cost of certain practices	Reflection on macroeconomic impacts Evaluation of investments to decarbonise agricultural machinery	Shows the market mechanisms that impact producer prices and household expenditure	Agenda on the support needed for farmers to encourage changes in practices Proxy for motivating the transition (including non-economic costs)
Limitations	Practical approach by practice, practices that do not involve changes to production systems or yield losses	Type of transition not suited to agriculture as it does not address the issue of operating costs + nothing on biodiversity	No consideration of production costs and necessary investments as such, nor of the changes required for the transition. No analysis of the industry.	Analysis of individual practices Does not reflect actual costs

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Why focus on a sectoral and regional case study?

Our interviews and bibliographic analysis showed the importance of describing the concrete changes in production tools linked to the transition. To do this, it is first necessary to describe and characterise these tools in detail. To establish such a description, available data requires to focus on a specific case study, concentrating on one sector in a given region.

Firstly, our interviews highlighted the need to study the transition at the sectoral level. Indeed, agri-food industries are very specific to each sector. For example, a slaughtering and cutting industry and a milling industry are completely different. Similarly, there is great disparity between different industries that process plant products. Some will be capital-intensive and based on a strategy of mass production of standardised volumes, such as starch production; others, on the contrary, will be labour-intensive and focused on strategies of qualitative differentiation, such as bakeries. Furthermore, a biodiversity-friendly scenario will have different consequences from one sector to another. If we focus on the field crop sector, some industries will see their supply volumes decrease and others increase.

Secondly, the industrial apparatus is interconnected with the region in which it develops (Gardin et al., 2024). Indeed, industrial tools offer opportunities for farmers, allowing certain crops to develop. On the other hand, industries are dependent on their supply. For some sectors, raw materials are difficult to transport, making industries completely dependent on local agriculture. Other raw materials are easily transportable, but rising energy costs favour local sourcing. However, agriculture also depends on the agro-ecological possibilities specific to each region. Thus, the crops and agri-food industries present are specific to each region.

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5. Result 3: Case study

Description of the study region and agri-food industries

Agro-ecological description: a region of contrasts between chalky plains with high yield potential and intermediate areas

Champagne-Ardenne (ChA) has a diverse range of landscapes where different land uses have developed (Champagne-Ardenne Region et al., 2001), with varying production potential and different types of farming systems. Figure 2 below shows the dominant agricultural orientation by municipality with the main agricultural regions of the ChA. We can see the presence of different zones: (i) two wine-growing areas, (ii) the chalky plains with high yield potential where industrial crops have developed, and (iii) the northern Ardennes and Haute-Marne, intermediate regions with more limited potential, where mixed farming and mixed livestock farming have developed.

Figure 2 : agricultural regions and dominant agricultural practices – Source: Agreste 2010 and author's annotations

Description of the local industrial fabric

Various agri-food industries have developed in Champagne-Ardenne. Agricultural production and the industrial fabric are closely linked for the major crops in this region. The establishment of certain industries has enabled the development of the crops they process, as was the case with the sugar industry in the 1950s and hemp processing in the 1970s in Champagne-Ardenne (de La

Teyssonnière, 2014) . Conversely, the guarantee of high production volumes, thanks to high yield potential, has led to the creation of one of Europe's largest bioeconomy complexes in Bazancourt, with a view to developing new agricultural outlets (Thénot & Honorine, 2017) . The link between agricultural production and industrial processing is all the more secure as most industrial sites belong to agricultural cooperatives (Thénot et al., 2018) .

Figure3 maps the main agri-food industries in Champagne-Ardenne. It can be seen that industries processing field crops have mainly developed in the Champagne-Crayeuse region.

In terms of job provision, the main agro-industrial processing facilities in Champagne are: four sugar refineries, with associated distilleries; animal feed processing plants, including five alfalfa dehydration plants; two starch factories, including a potato starch factory, which is scheduled to close at the end of 2024, and a wheat starch factory; two main flour mills; two malting plants; a potato processing plant; a distillery processing sugar factory and wheat by-products [N.B. Other distilleries are included in sugar factory jobs]; a rapeseed crushing plant; a corn mill; a hemp processing plant.

Figure3 : Map of the main industries processing field crops in Champagne-Ardenne

In Figure4, we have traced the flows of raw materials processed by the agri-food industries in Champagne-Ardenne. We have assumed that industries primarily process volumes produced in the region, and that anything not processed by industries is exported outside Champagne-Ardenne or consumed internally. Anything exported outside Champagne-Ardenne may be processed in a neighbouring region or exported internationally.

Les flux vers les industries en 2020

Figure 4 : flow of raw materials processed by industries in 2020

The volume processed by sugar refineries and rapeseed crushing plants exceeds the agricultural volumes produced in the region, meaning that some of the raw materials are imported from other regions (30% of beet and 50% of rapeseed processed). This map highlights some of the region's specific characteristics:

1. Firstly, certain industries are typical of north-eastern France, such as potato processing, starch production, sugar production and malt production. More specific to Champagne-Ardenne, alfalfa dehydration and hemp processing are well established there.
2. Secondly, a significant proportion of production is processed for non-food uses (the starch industry, biofuel production by distilleries and rapeseed crushing, hemp processing). This is in line with the development of outlets for the bioeconomy, driven by cooperatives in the region (Thénot & Honorine, 2017) .
3. Finally, it should be noted that the proportion of grain used in animal feed production is very low compared to the national average. Manufacturers generate numerous co-products that are used in animal feed.

The biophysical scenario

To achieve a high level of biodiversity, we developed an agricultural scenario for the Champagne-Ardenne region with the same crop rotation diversification objectives as in the BODIVA model. This corresponds to a high degree of crop diversification. The Figure 5 shows the evolution of land use in Champagne-Ardenne under such a set of assumptions. The areas under primary cereals, beet, oilseeds and potatoes are decreasing in favour of areas under permanent and temporary grassland, protein crops, dehydrated alfalfa, hemp and secondary cereals. Similarly, Figure 7 shows the evolution of crop rotation between 2020 and the biodiversity-friendly scenario. A significant proportion of the crop rotation is dedicated to fodder production, with 26% of the area still under grass (an increase of 40%), 8% of the crop rotation under temporary grassland (an increase of 125%), and 2% under fresh alfalfa. This change in crop rotation is consistent with the BIODIVA model: the increase in areas still covered by grassland makes it possible to achieve the target of at least 20% semi-natural vegetation in the landscape ; and increasing the proportion of protein crops (in PT or alfalfa) makes it possible to increase the proportion of symbiotically fixed nitrogen, thereby reducing the need for mineral nitrogen, which has a significant impact. These changes in crop rotation go hand in hand with developments in livestock farming systems, in terms of (1) extensification of

ruminant systems and (2) relocation of animal feed production in line with a circular approach (Garcia-Vega et al, 2024). These changes will also have significant consequences for the animal industries, which we do not analyse in detail here. Similarly, although the area under fruit trees and vegetables is increasing, we will not discuss the implications for the collection and processing of these products in the region.

Figure5 : Change in land area in Champagne-Ardenne between 2020 and the biodiversity-friendly 2050 scenario

Figure6 : Change in volumes in Champagne-Ardenne between 2020 and the biodiversity-friendly scenario for 2050

Figure6 shows the change in volume between 2020 and the biodiversity-friendly scenario. Declining volumes will have consequences for the supply of existing food processing industries, while growing volumes represent new opportunities for processing. We will examine this in the next section.

Figure7 : Changes in crop rotation in Champagne-Ardenne between 2020 and the 2050 scenario

Given that we will be focusing on arable crops in the rest of the study, Table 4 below shows the change in area and volume of arable crops in Champagne-Ardenne under the modeled scenario.

3 : Changes in the area and volume of field crops in Champagne-Ardenne

Crop	Area in 2020 (ha)	Area in 2050 (ha)	Volume 2020 (kt)	Volume in 2050 (kt)	Change in volume 2020-2050
soft wheat	373,618	175,778	2,925	1,309	-55
Barley (winter, spring, brewing)	292,540	128,354	1,982	851	-57
grain maize	49,577	37,470	381	287	-25
Starch potatoes	5,625	0	197	0	-100
Potatoes for consumption	14,020	8,412	717	363	-49
sugar beet	100,979	41,298	8,177	3,338	-59
rapeseed	127,299	53,351	407	170	-58
sunflower	23,249	36,614	53	82	55
PT alfalfa	62,349	153,830	561	1,384	147

Hemp	8,164	38,771	52	248	375
soy	4,572	25,403	8	40	417
peas (winter, spring)	31,843	76,070	137	326	138
Lentils (including seeds)	5,860	29,673	9	46	406
winter field beans	2,473	10,562	4	16	312
triticale	6,496	26,248	32	132	314
oats	8,115	34,739	33	143	330
rye	1,116	5,141	4	20	364
Durum wheat	262	481	1	2	75

Impact of the scenario on regional industries

Introduction

The impact of the scenario on regional industries was assessed in several stages. First, the scenario involves a change in crop rotation with significant crop diversification. This change in crop rotation leads to a change in *the product mix*, i.e. the quantity and nature of agricultural production. This change in the product mix alters the volumes allocated to agri-food industries compared to the current situation. The variation in allocated volumes has different consequences for industries, depending on the current state and evolution of the product mix in the scenario. Four configurations are possible in the territory, which led us to classify industries into three main types:

- Total volumes are decreasing but are sufficient to supply existing industries. Industries are maintained but their production costs are likely to increase. These are the industries that are maintained. This concerns primary cereal and potato. The industrial sectors involved are milling, starch production, distilling, malting, corn production, and potato processing for consumption.
- Total volumes are declining and are insufficient to supply existing industries. Some of these industries have to wind down their operations, leading to job losses and stranded assets. These are industries in decline. This concerns industrial beet and rapeseed crops. The industrial sectors involved are sugar refining and rapeseed crushing, as well as the production of biofuel, bioethanol and biodiesel.
- Total volumes increase to supply industries that are either already well established, but need to scale up (industrial hemp and dehydrated alfalfa); or that need to be developed nearly from scratch as they are not so present in the region – such as protein crops (peas, soya, field beans, lentils) and secondary cereals (triticale, oats, rye). This will require new investments and create new jobs.

For each type, we have characterized in more details the sectors concerned, their specific features and challenges. We then presented the changes in volumes at stake. Next, we assessed the social and economic consequences for industries, particularly in terms of jobs and stranded assets/investments. Finally, we identified the various challenges raised by these changes that public policies must address.

Sectors that are maintained

Presentation of sectors and their characteristics

Some crops are set to decline in a biodiversity-friendly scenario, but production volumes will still be sufficient to supply industry. This applies to primary cereals, wheat, barley, maize and potatoes. A significant proportion of the volume of these crops is destined for export. A decline in volumes would reduce exports but not industrial use.

Primary cereals are the main crops grown in France and represent significant volumes. They account for 27% of utilised agricultural area and 43% of arable land (calculation based on Agreste,

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2021). Cereals have historically benefited from support through the CAP, which has encouraged their expansion in Europe (Thomas et al., 2013) . These crops are easily transportable and geared towards commodity markets, particularly exports – the main destination for primary cereals in France (50% of wheat, 64% of barley and 33% of maize(calculation based on Interceréales, 2023)). Besides exports, these crops are used for four main industrial purposes: (1) animal feed, which accounts for 12% to 34% of the total uses of these crops at the national level, with a lot of substitutability between crops); (2) milling, (3) starch production, and (4) malting. Yet, only a limited proportion of the total volumes produced regionally are processed in Champagne Ardennes – below 20% for all crops. This is why even though volumes decrease, existing facilities could still run at full capacity under the biodiversity-friendly scenarios.

The same applies to potatoes – which remains a marginal crop in France, representing 0.7% of French UAA (calculation based on Agreste, 2021), and whose production is either exported (for 23% of the volumes produced) or consumed fresh (for 43% of the volumes – calculation based on FranceAgriMer, 2022). As with primary cereals, the share of volumes produced for industry (processing for human consumption and starch production) represents around 20% of the volumes produced.

For these sectors, industrial capacity is maintained in the biodiversity-friendly scenario. However, as raw materials would become scarcer, this could lead to an increase in their price and require accompanying policies to maintain the competitiveness of industrial players.

Main changes in production volumes under a biodiversity-friendly scenario in Champagne-Ardenne

In the biodiversity-friendly scenario, the volumes of these crops will decrease by almost 60%, with the exception of grain maize, which is grown on a small scale in Champagne-Ardenne in 2020. As the potato starch factory is currently closing down, we have assumed that there will be no more starch potato production in Champagne-Ardenne. Potato production for consumption will fall by 50%.

Crop	Area in 2020 (ha)	Area scenario (ha)	Volume in 2020 (kt)	Volume scenario (kt)	Change 2020-scenario
Wheat	373,618	175,778	2,925	1,309	-55
Barley	292,540	128,354	1,982	851	-57
Maize	49,577	37,470	381	287	-25%
Potato	19,649	8,412	913	363	-60

Impact on industries and social and economic needs

The industries that process these crops in the region are: two flour mills, a wheat starch factory, a wheat and beet distillery, three malt houses, a corn semolina factory, a potato starch factory and a potato processing plant. Livestock feed manufacturers also process primary cereals, but this represents very low grain volumes in Champagne-Ardenne (around 1% of production). This is due to the high availability of industrial co-products intended for animal feed and the fact that farms in the region produce a significant proportion of their feed in mixed farming structures.

In the scenario, the volumes destined for local industries are maintained and the industries themselves are also maintained. However, there is a risk of closure for one distillery, which processes both wheat and sugar mill by-products. Indeed, given that some of the region's sugar beet refineries are at risk of closure (seeSectors in decline), the sustainability of supplies of by-products could be called into question. This issue is discussed below with the sugar industries. In addition, Tereos announced the closure of its potato starch factory several years ago (Tereos, 2023) . The industrial site is to be taken over by a potato producer and trader who will rehabilitate part of the site as a storage and packaging centre (France Bleu, 2024) . Despite this takeover, a large part of the site will no longer be usable, resulting in stranded assets and job losses – independently from the scenario, though. The Tereos group's decision clearly shows that, in the face of more difficult economic conditions, the viability of industrial facilities is directly called into question.

Key issues for public policy

In the biodiversity-friendly scenario, the decline in total production volumes could lead to an increase in raw material costs. This could call into question profitability strategies based on mass

production. This concerns all industries in the region that process large volumes, but particularly the starch, distillery and livestock feed sectors, which find it difficult to differentiate themselves on the basis of quality. Public policies are therefore needed to support these industries.

The biodiversity-friendly scenario also significantly reduces exports of cereals and potatoes. This has a major impact on French trade and the trade balance. It requires a rethink of trade policy. Furthermore, although France accounts for only 6% of global cereal exports (calculated using FAOstat, 2020), it plays an important role in supplying certain import-dependent countries, particularly in North Africa (Interceréales, 2022) . Such a scenario will impact the supply strategy of these countries¹ .

In conclusion, although industrial capacity is being maintained, public policy will need to take action at various levels:

- Support for industrial capacity in the face of rising production costs
- Support for purchasing power in the face of rising food prices
- Reconsideration of trade strategies

Sectors in decline

Presentation of sectors and their characteristics

Certain crops are destined to decline in a biodiversity-friendly scenario. Production volumes would then be insufficient to supply current industries. In Champagne-Ardenne, this is the case for sugar beet, used for sugar production, and rapeseed, used for crushing and then biofuel production. In Champagne-Ardenne, there are four sugar refineries and one rapeseed crushing plant, which already supply part of their volumes from outside Champagne Ardennes. A decline in volumes as envisaged in our scenario will cause these industries to face supply disruptions and therefore calls into question their maintenance.

Historically, agricultural production and industrial tools have developed simultaneously within these sectors. The two are closely linked. Sugar beet has developed in regions suitable for its cultivation, where sugar factories have been set up to guarantee their supply in terms of both quantity and quality. Almost 100% of the beet produced in France is processed by French sugar factories or distilleries (Culture sucre, 2025) . Conversely, the development of industrial capacities has driven agricultural production up through contract farming. This is also the case in the rapeseed sector (Thomas et al., 2013): 70% of rapeseed produced in France is indeed crushed (Terres Univia, 2025). As agricultural production and industrial tools are closely linked, a change in production volume has a direct impact on industrial tools.

These two sectors – rapeseed and sugar beet – have also been heavily regulated by public policies: quotas for the sugar sector, lifted only in 2017; industrial set-aside for rapeseed after the MacSharry reform of 1992; and an incorporation mandate for biofuel, ensuring an outlet for these two crops (in bioethanol or biodiesel).² As a result, many sugar refineries have developed distillation units alongside sugar production in order to convert sugar refinery co-products into alcohol and diversify their outlets. Rapeseed crushing units are mainly focused on biodiesel production.

For these sectors, by-products are also important and contribute to the economic balance of the industries. The by-products of sugar refineries are beet pulp, which is used as animal feed; green juice, either used in ethanol production or as molasses by the fermentation industry; and skimmings used for fertilisation (Ceresco & Pivert, 2023; Idele, 2021) . The use of juice for ethanol production has

¹ The rise in production costs may also impact food prices for consumers, which may require public support – a measure that falls outside the scope of this paper.

² In 2005, the incorporation of biofuel became mandatory, with a target of 7% by 2020. Then, in 2015, this target was revised to 15% by 2030 (Aubert et al., 2018; Thomas et al., 2013) . More recently, France has also excluded the manufacture of biofuel from palm and soybean oils, favouring the use of rapeseed (Geffray et al., 2023) . All these policies have helped to guarantee outlets for biofuels. This has structured the biofuel market and encouraged the development of industrial tools.

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prompted sugar refineries to invest in distilleries. For rapeseed, rapeseed meal or cakes are used as animal feed and accounts for half the weight of rapeseed.

Finally, both sectors are export-oriented. Forty-one per cent of French sugar is exported (Culture sucre, 2025). Biodiesel exports are growing and accounted for around 26% of production in 2022 (calculation based on Geffray et al., 2023). However, bioessence exports are declining and accounted for 14% of bioessence production in 2022 (Ibid.). Overall, the biofuel sector has a trade deficit (Ibid.).

Main changes in production volumes under a biodiversity-friendly scenario in Champagne-Ardenne

In a biodiversity-friendly scenario, production volumes could fall by 60%.

Crop	Area in 2020 (ha)	Area in 2050 (ha)	Volume in 2020 (kt)	Volume in 2050 (kt)	Change 2020-2050
Sugar beet	100,979	41,298	8,177	3,338	-59
Rapeseed	127,299	53,351	407	170	-58

Impact on industries and social and economic needs

The decline in production volumes will have a direct impact on local industries.

Beets, which are rich in water, cannot be stored or moved: they must be processed directly nearby. The decrease in volume therefore implies a decline in supply for local industries and is likely to lead to the closure of two to three factories in the region (out of four).

The closure of the sugar factories will also lead to the closure of the attached distilleries. These are taken into account in the stranded assets and job losses of the sugar factories, with the exception of the Cristanol distillery. Cristanol has two processing lines, one for sugar factory co-products and one for wheat. If the adjacent sugar factory closes, the beet processing line will have to close. It is assumed that the distillery will not be sufficiently profitable with only one processing line in operation (the wheat line). Here we take the most pessimistic scenario, in which the Cristanol distillery also closes its doors.

Rapeseed can be easily stored and transported. Yet, assuming the evolution we consider will happen at the EU, or even at the French scale, the total volume of rapeseed available to French industries will go down, meaning that some crushing plants will have to wind down their operation. It is however difficult to predict which plants will remain open and which will close. We assume that, as the sector is in serious difficulty in our scenario, the plant in Champagne-Ardenne will close.

Sector	Closure	Economic implications		Social implications	
		Stranded assets	Need for investment	Job losses	Jobs created
Beet	Closure of 2 to 3 sugar factories	€1.2 billion		672	
Beet	Closure of distillery	€200 million		170	
Rapeseed	Closure of crushing plant	€118 million		90	
Total		€1,518 million		932	

For the sugar sector, stranded assets account for 27% of tangible fixed assets in the sugar sector in France. Job losses account for 13% of jobs in the sector in France and 77% of jobs in the sector in Champagne-Ardenne. Sugar refineries are the largest employers among the region's primary processing agri-food industries (excluding wines and spirits). The closure of these industries will therefore have a significant economic and social impact locally and will require accompanying measures.

For the biodiesel sector, stranded assets account for 19% of tangible fixed assets of the sector, and job losses for 7%. However, some rapeseed processing companies are classified differently

Key issues for public policy

Under a biodiversity-friendly scenario, these two sectors will be in crisis and will need to be supported by public policy: social policies to support those who lose their jobs, training to enable employees losing their jobs to find new employment opportunities in other sectors (see below).

But the decline in sugar and biofuel volumes will also have economic consequences. If these products become scarcer, their prices are likely to rise. The increase in the price of sugar will directly impact consumers and secondary processing industries that use sugar. Nevertheless, this biodiversity-friendly scenario goes hand in hand with a significant shift in diets towards healthier diets that are less sugar-intensive. Consumers may be little affected by the price increase. On the other hand, secondary processing industries will face similar difficulties, with a decline in supply and demand. The decline in production would also lead to a decline in by-products used for animal feed (sugar pulp and rapeseed cakes). Livestock feed manufacturers will therefore have to change their supply strategy. They are however likely to find alternatives thanks to the development in protein crop production (see below), which are however likely to be more expensive.

Furthermore, as both sectors are export-oriented, the decline in production will have an impact on France's trade balance.

The biofuel sector has been strongly supported by public policy. The use of agricultural raw materials for biofuel production is already controversial. This biodiversity-friendly scenario also calls these policies into question .

In conclusion, public policies will have to respond to various challenges:

- Social support for people losing their jobs
- Changing current decarbonisation policies in the transport sector
- Support for industries dependent on products and co-products from these sectors (secondary processing industries using sugar, distilleries, FAB)
- Support for changes in diets towards less sugary diets

Sectors to be developed

Presentation of sectors and their characteristics

Certain crops that allow for crop diversification favourable to a high level of biodiversity are already being promoted within promising sectors. In Champagne-Ardenne, this is the case for dehydrated alfalfa and hemp. These crops still represent a small part of crop rotation (3% and 1% of UAA in ChA, respectively). Nevertheless, these sectors are well established and are set to continue their development in a biodiversity-friendly scenario.

Both of these industries are characteristic of the Champagne-Ardenne region, which currently accounts for most of France's production (the ChA region represents 75% of dehydrated alfalfa production and 50% of hemp production in France). Industrial primary processing facilities were developed in the 1960s and 1970s to create new outlets for these crops. This enabled these crops to be maintained and then developed. Conversely, the industrial facilities were able to continue operating by securing their supply through multi-year contracts with farmers.

Production and industrial tools are interdependent here. Indeed, hemp and alfalfa cannot be easily transported after harvesting, so the first stage of processing must necessarily take place close to where they are produced. Once the first stage of processing has been completed, the products can be easily transported for consumption or undergo a second stage of processing outside the region.

In order to survive and ensure a profitable price for farmers, these industries have been able to adapt. They have improved their competitiveness and found new outlets for their products. They have also been able to equip themselves with research and development tools, enabling them to better promote their production. They are not currently suffering from a lack of outlets. Nevertheless, developing demand remains a major challenge for the growth of these sectors.

Changes between 2020 and 2050 in Champagne-Ardenne

In the scenario, these crops are growing strongly, with alfalfa production increasing by 145% and hemp production by 375%.

Crop	Area in 2020 (ha)	Area scenario (ha)	Volume in 2020 (kt)	Volume scenario (kt)	Change 2020-scenario
Dehydrated alfalfa	50,995	124,785	459	1,123	+145
Hemp	8,164	38,771	52	248	+375

Impact on industries and social and economic needs

The development of these crops requires the development of new industrial tools, based on existing models, to process and add value to the additional volumes. This will require investments of around €678 million and the creation of 865 jobs.

Sector	Tools to be developed	Economic implications		Social implications	
		Stranded assets	Need for investment	Job losses	Jobs created
Alfalfa	12 new dehydration units		€553 million		642
Hemp	4 new production lines		€125 million		223
Total			€678 million		865

Key issues for public policy

It became apparent that in order to develop these sectors already established in the region, it will be necessary to address needs at three levels:

- to support the development in agricultural production
- to support the development of strong enough facilities at the processing level
- to support a growth in the demand

Indeed, beyond the strict need for investment to create new processing units, the development of these sectors poses several challenges.

Firstly, the main challenge identified by stakeholders in these sectors is ensuring sufficient demand. Their products face fierce competition in an undifferentiated market (Meynard et al., 2018) . To develop outlets for their products and be more competitive, various strategies have already been put in place and must be supported by public policy.

- The development of existing markets. The most significant obstacle to market development is the competitiveness of products compared to other less expensive but less sustainable products. Given the sustainability of products from these sectors, they should be promoted through a policy of demand support. (E.g. a policy of incorporating biomass materials into the construction or apparel sectors to support the hemp industry; better regulation of the market for animal feed products to support the alfalfa industry). The structuring and promotion of the industry can also play a role.
- Reducing production costs . This would enable these sectors to be more competitive with currently competing products and thus increase demand. Historically, these sectors have already been able to adapt (e.g., alfalfa dehydration plants have merged and reduced their energy consumption in response to rising fossil fuel costs). Public policy has already played a role, for example, in supporting the decarbonisation of dehydration plants. Raw materials also represent a key cost for manufacturers. Support for production, which already exists in the form of coupled aid, indirectly reduces the cost of raw materials.
- The creation of new markets. (E.g. the use of hemp in the construction sector, developed in the 1990s). This creates a need for research and development to develop new products and new industrial processes. It also requires to organise and structure the sector.
- Qualitative differentiation of products. This also requires research and development. These sectors have already embarked on quality initiatives (e.g. the dehydrated alfalfa sector has developed products with higher protein content, better traceability, and product differentiation according to animal species (de La Teyssonnière, 2014)). Nevertheless, quality markets are often limited in volume and this can only be a complementary strategy – not the core of it.

Secondly, the industrial tool itself needs to be supported. In our scenario, the creation of new production tools requires significant investment. This needs to be supported by public policy. The industrial tool can also be supported by reducing its production costs and coordinating the various players in the sector.

Lastly, these sectors need to secure the supply of raw material – but this comes last, as the existence of a demand is likely to trigger a growth in the production. There is currently good vertical integration between producers and primary processing plants through multi-year contracts. However, several levers can be improved:

- Research and development. These crops are currently minor crops that suffer from a lack of research and development. Better research and development would increase yields and improve practices, in particular to adapt production to the needs of industries and markets (e.g. the recent textile sector for hemp requires a different technical approach from other sectors) – thus potentially increasing gross value added for those crops;
- Economic support for production. Support for production makes these crops more competitive with crops that are more profitable for farmers. Depending on the market, the prices paid to producers can vary greatly from one year to the next. Support for production makes these crops more attractive to producers. Alfalfa and hemp already benefit from

coupled aid. This could be increased in order to make these crops more competitive for farmers.

In conclusion, public policies can act at various levels to support the development of these virtuous sectors:

- Support for production
- Support for research and development, both in terms of agricultural production and the creation of new products
- Support for investment to create new industrial tools
- Support for manufacturers, in particular by reducing their production costs
- Support for the organisation and coordination of sectors
- Support for demand

Sectors to be created

Presentation of sectors and their characteristics

Certain crops are set to grow significantly in a biodiversity-friendly scenario, but are currently almost non-existent. This is the case for protein crops and minor cereals. Here we are studying peas, soya, lentils and field beans as protein crops, and triticale, oats and rye as minor cereals. In 2020, in Champagne-Ardenne, protein crops accounted for 3% of crop rotation, and minor cereals for 1%. At the French level, these protein crops represent 1.8% of UAA and these minor cereals 1.4% of UAA (Agreste, 2021).

These crops have limited to no dedicated facilities to be processed. However, protein extraction plants have emerged recently: Roquette has a pea extraction plant in Vic-sur-Aisne that processes 125 kt of peas, next to the Champagne-Ardenne region. The Cosucra factory in Belgium also processes pea protein and is located near Champagne-Ardenne. Smaller industrial facilities process small volumes of protein crops or secondary cereals, such as soybean crushing plants.

Apart from these few industries, the vast majority of protein crops and secondary cereals are consumed on the farm or processed by animal feed manufacturers, which tend to consider agricultural raw materials to be easily substitutable. These crops are therefore in direct competition with less expensive and more readily available raw materials, available in larger volumes. They thus suffer from a lack of competitiveness for manufacturers, but also at the farm level. Primary cereals are, in fact, more profitable for farmers.

Finally, these crops suffer from technical and socio-economic lock-in throughout the value chain (Magrini et al., 2016; Meynard et al., 2018). As these crops are rarely grown, they are little studied and face numerous obstacles to their production and promotion, from upstream to downstream (lack of varieties and crop protection methods, complexity and lack of references for their technical itineraries, logistical constraints on their collection and coordination difficulties throughout the value chain) (Ibid.). These obstacles are interconnected and reinforce each other. As a result, faced with these obstacles, actors in the value chain have little interest in producing or promoting them, and the less they are cultivated and processed, the more these obstacles are reinforced, and so on.

Changes between 2020 and 2050 in Champagne-Ardenne

All crops are expected to increase at least fourfold, except for peas, which are already well developed in Champagne-Ardenne (Table 4).

Table 4 : Changes in acreage and volume between 2020 and 2050

Crop	Area in 2020 (ha)	Area in 2050 (ha)	Volume in 2020 (kt)	Volume in 2050 (kt)	Change 2020-2050
Pea	31,843	76,070	137	326	+138
Lens	5,860	27,254	9	42	+365
Soy	4,572	25,403	8	40	+417
Faba beans	2,473	10,562	4	16	+312
Oat	8,115	34,739	33	143	+330

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Triticale	6,496	26,248	32	132	+314
Rye	1,116	5,141	4	20	+364

Impact on industries and social and economic needs

The promotion of protein crops and minor cereals involves creating new production tools and adapting the supply chain for existing industries.

As these crops do not currently have their own industrial tools, it is difficult to know how they could be processed. Nevertheless, we have made assumptions for each crop based on current market opportunities. Some of the outlets require the creation of new tools, while others require changes to the supply strategies of existing tools, sometimes requiring adaptations to incorporate a greater diversity of crops (Table5).

Table5 : assumptions regarding market opportunities and industrial needs for protein crops and coarse grains

Sector	Market assumptions	Industrial requirements
Peas	½ towards protein extraction	New tools needed to increase current capacity
	½ for animal feed	Adaptation of FABs
Lentils	For human consumption with minimal processing (whole seeds in bags, canned goods)	New tools required
Soya	Mostly for animal feed	New soybean crushing tools
	Minority for human consumption (soy foods and textured protein)	New tools needed
Field beans	Towards animal feed	Adaptation of FAB
Oats	¾ for animal feed (including own consumption)	Adaptation of FAB
	¼ for human consumption	New tools required
Triticale	For animal feed (including own consumption)	Adaptation of FAB
Rye	¾ for animal feed (including own consumption)	Adaptation of FAB
	¼ for human consumption	Adaptation of mills

We have calculated a portion of the investment and employment needs for the new tools required in Champagne-Ardenne. This calculation corresponds to the needs for creating tools capable of processing the additional volumes produced in the region. For secondary cereals, we consider that knowledge of existing tools and the low volumes in ChA do not allow for calculation assumptions. Table6 presents the needs for new processing tools.

6 : Processing tools to be created for protein crops, with investment and employment requirements

Sector	Tools to be created	Economic implications		Social implications	
		Stranded assets	Need for investment	Job losses	Jobs created
Pea	New protein extraction capacity		€269 million		135
Soya	Crush unit		€7 million		1
	New capacity for human consumption		€24 million		1
Lentils	New capacity for minimally processed human food products		€12 million		4

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Total			€312 million		194
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Investment requirements for protein extraction amount to €290 million (peas and soya). This corresponds to 8% of the tangible fixed assets of industries manufacturing starchy products. The jobs created represent 3% of jobs in the sector. Such a processing unit would be as large as Roquette's current pea extraction plant in Vic-sur-Aisne, the main protein extraction plant in France.

Key issues for public policy

In their analysis of the barriers to the development of secondary crops, Meynard et al. (2018) suggest several avenues for developing these sectors. They consider that income support for farmers alone is not sufficient. In their view, products from these sectors must move away from commodity markets and benefit from differentiation. This requires an adaptation of standards and quality labels. Good coordination between actors in the value chain is also necessary. Finally, there is a need for genetic, agronomic, technological and organisational innovation to remove obstacles to the development of these sectors, which requires research. Given the volumes envisaged in our scenario, it is difficult to assume that the development of these sectors will only come about through qualitative differentiation, which, by definition, require markets of limited size. Other forms of demand support must therefore be considered.

In a context where most of the outlets for these crops are in the feed industry, this raises the question of whether it is possible to replace imported soybean meal, which is cheap and readily available in large quantities, with local production³. All other things being equal, this would require a significant reduction of the competitiveness gap with Brazilian soybeans, which seems unlikely in the short and even medium term. Conversely, harmonising production standards, which would increase the production costs of imported soybeans, or protecting the European market, even temporarily, could be part of a mix of solutions. For feed manufacturers, this would have three consequences: an increase in raw material costs; a change in their logistics; and *ultimately* an increase in their production costs. Public policies will be needed to support these changes, which will also have significant effects on livestock farming systems. These are not addressed in this study.

The second outlet for these crops is human consumption. The increase in human consumption of protein crops and coarse grains, compatible with a biodiversity-friendly scenario, requires a significant change in diet. This is detailed in previous studies (Aubert, Gardin, Alliot, et al., 2021; Poux & Aubert, 2018). It also requires public policies to support changes in diet.

These "to be created" sectors face similar issues to those "to be developed". The public policies to be mobilised are quite similar. These sectors are still partly to be invented, which requires additional efforts to create, almost from scratch, value-added sectors and organise the actors in the value chain.

In conclusion, public policies must act at different levels to support the creation of these new sectors:

- Support for production
- Support for research and development, both in terms of agricultural production and the creation of new products
- Support for investment to create new industrial tools
- Support for manufacturers, in particular by reducing their production costs
- Support for the organisation and coordination of sectors
- Support for demand (reducing the price competitiveness gap, changing diets)

³ In a context where France has a deficit in protein-rich animal feed of 40% to 50% depending on the year (Terres Univia, 2024).

6. Discussion

Our case study shows the consequences of a biodiversity-friendly scenario on the industrial fabric of a particular region. We draw three points for discussion from this.

Firstly, the biodiversity-friendly scenario is positive for this region from both an environmental and a socio-economic perspective. The modelled crop rotation allows for significant re-diversification and increased complexity of landscapes, as well as a sharp reduction in the use of synthetic mineral nitrogen. This creates more favourable conditions for the development of biodiversity. This scenario also improves the circularity of agricultural products by consolidating regional exchanges between plant and animal production. In addition to the environmental gains, this scenario is positive for the region from a social perspective. While some industries will close, resulting in the loss of more than 900 jobs, new industries will be created, generating more than 1,000 jobs. Thus, new economic opportunities could surpass the negative impacts, though upon a number of conditions.

Such transformations of the local industrial fabric require indeed significant policy support. The public policies at stake in this scenario are important and varied. They relate not only to industrial issues as such, but also to issues of demand, research, sector organisation, agricultural production, employment and trade. Furthermore, depending on the type of industries concerned, the supporting policies will differ, e.g. industrial policies may concern maintaining the competitiveness of existing industries or meeting the investment needs of others. Each policy could be the subject of a detailed study. While certain policies are already discussed in existing studies, such as support for agricultural production or research, our analysis shows the importance of establishing ambitious policies that influence demand. Indeed, certain historical examples have shown the limitations of policies focused solely on supporting production. For example, the 2014-2020 Plant Protein Plan for France aimed to increase legume production in France by increasing subsidies for their production and supporting research and training (MAAF, 2014) . Unfortunately, this policy has not had the desired effect, as legume production has not increased significantly in France since 2014 (France stratégie, 2024) . Policies supporting demand are all the more important given that the economic opportunities offered by this scenario rely on the development of sectors that currently suffer from a lack of competitiveness and demand. Nevertheless, in the current economic climate, a policy that influences demand through market regulation seems difficult to endorse. Another historical example of demand support that has enabled the development of an industry and its industrial fabric is the development of biofuels. Several policies to incorporate biofuels into transport have been implemented, with quantified targets and economic incentives through tax exemptions for these biofuels. This has led to the development of rapeseed crushing plants and distilleries processing wheat and beet co-products. Such a policy could be considered for certain sectors such as hemp, with targets for incorporating biomaterials into construction.

Finally, we have looked at the regional level, but what about the national level? While this study has provided a detailed characterisation of the industries present in a given territory, the results of the scenario are specific to this region and its industrial tools. Applying the same method to another region with a different industrial network will yield different results. At the national level, some results are likely to be similar, while others will differ. Declining and growing volumes will be different, as will the sectors at risk and those poised for growth. Certain regional specificities, such as the presence of the hemp and dehydrated alfalfa sectors, will not develop as much at the national scale. One sector which would deserve more attention in the future is that of feed manufacturing – which was only partially covered here due to its limited importance in Champagne-Ardenne. Nevertheless, on a national scale, the volumes of primary cereals allocated to FABs in Champagne-Ardenne are significant (i.e., 13% of wheat, 12% of barley and 34% of maize(calculation based on Interceréales, 2023) . Feed manufacturers could therefore be severely impacted by a decline in primary cereal volumes, leading to job losses – all the more that all biodiversity friendly scenarios also entail a strong restructuring of the livestock sector, away from concentrate feeds. The evolution of the feed manufacturing sector should thus be thought along with that of the livestock sector which, in biodiversity friendly scenarios, tend towards a decrease in monogastric production and an extensification of ruminant farming. Livestock feed requirements will therefore be different. Such

changes could lead to job losses within FABs, which currently represent 15,000 jobs (SNIA, 2024) . At the national level, such a scenario could therefore be negative in socio-economic terms, as job opportunities would not compensate for job losses.

Furthermore, the change in crop rotation in this scenario has a significant impact on French exports. Crops for which France is currently a net exporter, such as wheat, will see their exports drastically reduced. However, according to (Schiavo et al., 2021) , in a biodiversity-friendly scenario such as the one we have modelled, the European Union becomes a net exporter of calories, through changes in diets (with a reduction in calories consumed) and a reduction in imports (particularly soybean meal). The social and economic conditions enabling such a change also require strong public policies (these policies must enable a significant change in diet and preserve the price competitiveness of European legumes) (Ibid.). A detailed analysis of the necessary policies is not developed in this study.

Compared to the existing literature, this study provides insights into the transformations at stake for the agri-food industries in a biodiversity-friendly transition. It fills the gap in analyses of the role of the agri-food industries in the transition. It also highlights the changes in production tools linked to the transition, which are rarely identified in the literature. Finally, this study assesses the economic needs and social consequences of a biodiversity-friendly transition for agriculture, analyses that are still rare in the literature, proposing a new methodology. Nevertheless, our economic analysis could be further developed to better understand the economic consequences of the transition.

With regard to the expectations of policy makers, our study responds by highlighting (i) the changes at stake in each sector for industrial infrastructure, and (ii) by assessing the social and economic consequences of these changes. This provides an understanding of the level of transformation involved in a biodiversity-friendly scenario, with its social and economic consequences, and distinguishes between the losing and winning sectors. These elements provide information on the level of public support required and the sectors most in need of assistance. It also reveals the sectors whose current development is not compatible with biodiversity-friendly agriculture but which receive public support, pointing to the public policy changes needed for these sectors.

Nevertheless, this study describes the issues requiring public policy support but does not present concrete public policy proposals. Only the cost in terms of investment required to create new processing units has been assessed. However, as the policies raised are numerous and varied, they are difficult to use to provide concrete advice to policy makers. Further analyses are needed to design the required public and explore how they could be implemented.

Furthermore, this study raises macroeconomic questions such as the competitiveness of industries and France, but it does not assess the macroeconomic consequences of the scenario in economic terms.

Finally, while this study presents a socially positive narrative at the regional level, it is difficult to apply at the national level. It seems difficult to apply this method at the national level because it requires a detailed analysis of the current industrial fabric. On the other hand, applying the same method to another region with different characteristics would provide a better understanding of the mechanisms at play.

We thus identify two ways in which one can build on this study's results:

- Further designing key public policies to be implemented by studying the deployment of certain public policy instruments. The incorporation mandate applied to biomaterials in construction has already been identified as one of the key instruments.
- The development of similar analyses in other regions in order to deepen knowledge of the mechanisms at play and the public policies required.

7. Conclusions

In conclusion, if we focus on the agri-food industry, a biodiversity-friendly scenario has positive environmental and social impacts for the Champagne-Ardenne region. This scenario entails significant changes to the existing industrial fabric, involving factory closures, but also economic opportunities that create jobs. Most sectors will need to adapt their economic strategy. The public policies needed to support these transformations are both significant and varied. However, the development of demand-focused public policies emerges as an important issue for the agri-food industries. These policies are all the more important given that the sectors to be developed in a biodiversity-friendly scenario are currently suffering from a lack of demand. At the national level, this biodiversity-friendly scenario may be socially negative, particularly as the animal feed manufacturing sector would be severely disrupted.

By highlighting the changes at stake for the agri-food industries in a biodiversity-friendly scenario, assessing the socio-economic impacts of these changes, and highlighting the issues raised that public policies must address, this study meets a number of expectations of policy makers. To take this further, detailing the most important public policy instruments and extending the study to other regions would complement this analysis and better meet the expectations of policy makers.

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